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LAW MAKING WITHIN THE WTO AND STATE SOVEREIGNTY: EMERGING CONCEPTS

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Abstract

Sovereignty is a major concern in international law which affects and regulates internal affairs (domestic) and foreign (international) affairs of countries globally. Policies and laws at international level especially on trade are products of international organizations, multi-corporations, and institutions that appear to be strong and shape's internal affairs of the nation states. Opinion of jurists and theorists in international economic law discipline argue that the law making within the nation state is being distorted to the extent that internal power to regulate domestic affairs in trade are submitted to these global institutions mostly by stronger economies and vigorously explained as hegemonic. Global organizations are seen to be coding certain constitutional norms to self-generate ambiguous treaty provisions that might not be fully captured as against the powers of states. Some theorists do not place much emphasis to international organization's capacity to develop autonomous capacities to produce, monitor and enforce legal norms in domestic affairs. How can this be achieved? For instance, Anti-dumping Agreement being a trade relief provided by the WTO must be made in accordance with its objectives for any member state willing to domesticate same. This may amount to ousting the sovereign power to deal in internal law making. This article analyses these arguments by employing doctrinal and descriptive approach. The article further finds that WTO is overextended and

in danger of losing authority and legitimacy as global trade arbiter. It also finds that the transfer of the state of certain sovereign rights and authorities to supranational structures does not mean the restriction of sovereign rights. It went ahead to recommend that ADA being a trade remedy should be a matter of choice and based on individual's member state's peculiarity. The article also recommends the abolition of Amicus Curie in Disputes Settlement; allow full participation of member state's actors before final determination of cases. It concluded that for WTO to continue to be relevant as global trade regulator certain policy and instrument need to be revisited in order to enable the developing economies shape their legal regimes based on their respective peculiarities as advocated by liberalists as proponents of "new Sovereignty".

Key words: Sovereignty, Law Making, WTO, ADA, GATT, Constitutional norms.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

The paper examines the law making within the WTO and the emerging concepts in line with the principles of sovereignty in globalized world and how nations submit to WTO jurisdictions in the application of internal regulations. The objective of this paper is to analyze the opposing views on the emerging concepts amongst members within the domestic law making processes and the sovereign rights of these individual members. It is also to situate the position that sovereignty does not prohibit international engagements rather supports inter-relationships amongst nation states.

Free trade being a concept designed as a result of trade liberalization allowed countries to reap the economic benefits outside their home states. Countries that allow imports must be ready to sacrifice certain legal regimes temporarily losing their sovereign powers for others to dictate economic policies and constitutional norms in their domestic affairs. This is not only restricted to trade but overlaps to human rights and security. Other views discard the establishment of WTO on pretext that it supports capitalistic ideology. Some theorists opine that WTO takes away the sovereign rights of individual member states while the opponents still maintain that members retain the sovereign rights to deal within/without the domestic affairs of their respective home state.

However, in this World of conflicting ideologies and economic supremacy between nation states in that industrialization and technology draw line as to who occupies what and the so-called developed and under-developed synthesis these conflicting interests between WTO members affecting trade rules in domestic affairs of the members would continue to dominate the working of WTO, it is imperative to have this kind of study so as to situate position for better understanding amongst members. This conflict was the underlying force that generated the idea of making GATT 1947, International Trade Organization, Uruguay Rounds, and Marrakech Agreement to the recent emergence of World Trade Organization in 1994 after. International law has set certain constraints as to what states can do, however, interventions by international institutions become prominent and eminent. It once said...;

However, for all the reasons mentioned already, the conditions under which sovereignty is exercised and practiced-have changed dramatically since 1945.

Many new states have emerged and are in the process of consolidating their identity.....And many new actors are playing international roles previously more or less the exclusive preserve of the states¹

This debate between proponents of absolute sovereignty and liberalists was ongoing; on one hand, theorist explained vigorously emerging concepts that explained sovereignty to mean hegemonic where major economies exploited the vulnerability of minor economies in the name of free trade at the same time concealing their borders for protection in favor of their local industries². The concept is still very crucial especially when discussing about international relation within the context of nation-state's "right" to monopolize certain exercises of power with respect to its territory and citizens as rightly observed by the 'old Westerphalian views'. The realists on the other hand, are of the view that interference in a national government's decisions and activities by foreign or international powers and authority³ should be avoided.

After the take up barely six years, WTO has been challenged for lack of democratic accountability, describing it as mere front for multinational corporations and dehumanizing capitalist values⁴. Second, its own institutional viability brought about constitutional flaws allowing it to set new rules at dispute settlement judgments which would diminish the existing rights and obligations for members⁵.

Similarly, a number of environmental agreements-many with trade sanctions as the compliance weapon of choice-has multiplied, resulting in plethora of international rules on matters such as hazardous wastes, the ozone layer, biological diversity, endangered species, wildlife, preservation, wetlands etc. This has already led to conflict between trade

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¹International Commission On Intervention and State Sovereignty (ICISS), *The Responsibility to Protect* (International Research Center Protect (International Development Research Centre, Canada2001) at 7.

²The U.S. participation and none member of some multi-lateral trade agreements is an eye-opener in this regard. It is the major beneficiary of ADA through Anti-dumping actions using measure as relief. Most WTO ADA cases emanated from U.S.

³ John H Jackson, *Sovereignty, the WTO, and Changing Fundamentals of International Law* (Cambridge University Press 2006) at 57.

⁴ Claude E Barfield, *Free Trade, Sovereignty, Democracy: The Future of the World Trade Organization* (2001) Vol.2 No.1,403.

⁵ Claude E Barfield, *ibid* at p.403.

and environmental rules, as demonstrated by the WTO Shrimp/Turtle and Tuna/Dolphin cases⁶.

John Jackson in March 2000 warned scholars of the international trading system against falling back on a series of “mantras” which in his opinion are phrases that “are used to avoid thinking certain issues through, listing sovereignty and government to government when describing the working of the WTO⁷. Recent debates regarding the impact of globalization on state sovereignty have led to some to conclude that globalization is eroding such sovereignty⁸. These are key issues which if untouched would erode the objectives of WTO and the paper aims to analyze these conflicting views and strike a balance.

1.1. SOVEREIGNTY AS AN EMERGING CONCEPT IN INTERNATIONAL TRADE:

The term sovereignty has always been susceptible to various meanings⁹. As originally expressed in the works of Machiavelli, Bodin, and Hobbes, it served as an attempt to localize a single supreme legislative and political authority within the internal structure of a polity. As a corollary to this theory, the term sovereignty came to describe not only the relationship between a supreme authority and its subjects within a state, but also the relationship of that authority with other states. Simply put, sovereignty could be considered a form of absolute domestic jurisdiction—the exclusion of external actors from domestic authority structured within a given territory¹⁰.

⁶ For further information on the case see Claude E Barfield: *Free Trade, Sovereignty, and Democracy: The Future of the World Trade Organization* (AEI2001); also available at <www.wto.org> accessed on 15th April, 2023.

⁷ Op cit note 3 p 409.

⁸ Duncan B Hollis, *Private Actors in Public International Law: Amicus Curiae And The Case For The Retention Of State Sovereignty*, Boston College of International and Comparative Law Review(2002)Vol.25,available at<<http://lawdigitalcommons.bc.edu/iclr/vol25/iss2/5>>accessed 15 April,2023.

⁹ Jack Goldsmith, *Sovereignty, International Relations Theory, and International Law: Sovereignty: Organized Hypocrisy*, 52 STAN. L. REV. 959, 959 (2000) (noting conventional wisdom that sovereignty in the sense of a nation's exclusive and absolute power within its territory "appears to have diminished significantly in the past half century as a result of economic globalization, transportation and communications advances, the rise of nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), and the spread of international human rights law"); Kal Raustiala *Sovereignty and Multilateralism*, 1 CHI.J. INT'L L. 401, 418-19 (2000) ("[W]e are increasingly choosing to regulate at the international level. ... Sovereignty traditionally conceived will necessarily be compromised....");

¹⁰ See Goldsmith, at 967 (noting that the traditional conception of sovereignty reflected the right of a state to determine its own Constitution, its own commercial policies, and to treat its subjects according to its discretion). Krasner notes that this concept of sovereignty is often called Westphalia sovereignty, although the principle that it reflects "had virtually nothing to do with the Peace of Westphalia." Accordingly, that term is not used herein.

Can we conceive “constitutional” norms at the global level beyond the nation-state? The global organizations seem to develop certain constitutional norms to self-generate ambiguous treaty provisions that might not be fully captured as against the state centeredness¹¹. International relation mainstream theorists have often refused to recognize an international organization’s capacity to develop autonomous capacities to produce, monitor and enforce legal norms¹².

The concept of sovereignty has been well captured in trade jurisprudence which carries a hallmark of the Lotus principle. Under the well-known principle of public international law, sovereign states are capable of doing whatever they desire as long as no explicit prohibition exists under international law¹³, a classical example is where a WTO member decides to implement Anti-dumping Agreement slightly deferring from the main text like in most developed economies as U.S while WTO insists on consistency¹⁴.

In traditional legal doctrine, sovereignty is the category which expresses the content and scope of the state in the domestic and foreign policy. The appearance of a new state automatically means the presence of its sovereignty. The loss of sovereignty leads to the termination of its existence as a subject of international law; as it cannot belong to anyone except state¹⁵.

The influence of international law is beginning to make itself felt in areas hitherto regarded as subject to the state’s exclusive jurisdiction. For instance, the creation of WTO and the allowance for the application of Anti-Dumping Agreement within the domestic affairs of the state further elaborates the state inclusiveness¹⁶. In international law, theorists support its exclusivity, possessed by the state, other opposing views are that certain exceptions do exist where the exclusivity is relaxed and the international law regulates in that regard. What then is sovereignty from the various arguments: from the perspective of

¹¹Weiler J.H; et al, “*European Constitutionalism and its Discontent* (1997) p354.

¹² Alec S S, “*Constitutionalism, Legal Pluralism, and International Regimes* (2009) IND. J. Global Legal Studies p 621.

¹³ S.S Lotus (*France v Turkey*), 1927 P.C.I.J, CHD,S; Global Constitutionalism of Country College of Law, Chicago- Kent, Illinois Institute of Technology Page 667.

¹⁴ This practice has been ignored mostly by the opponent of Anti-dumping actions, however more often than not mostly benefit from taking AD actions violating the AD Agreement. US, China, UK, India etc are at forefront.

¹⁵ Yunk, B, et al: “*The State sovereignty and Sovereign Rights: The Correlation Problem*” Man in India (2018), Research Gate: <https://www.researchgate.net/Publicatio/322233984> accessed on the 2nd August, 2022. (Abstract)

¹⁶ Ibid at P455; in the *Anglo-Norwegian Fisheries Case*: ICJ Reports, 1951, P116; 18 ILR, P.86.

International law theories and those whose opinions give exclusive jurisdiction to state in the domestic affairs?

2.0. DEFINITION OF SOVEREIGNTY

According to Black's Law Dictionary the word is derived from the word "sovereign or Sovran" to mean a person body, or state vested with independent and supreme political authority of an independent state. It also means the state itself, supreme dominion, authority, or rule¹⁷. Such definitions may be confusing; it is well to distinguish the senses in which the word sovereignty is used. It means supremacy in the ordinary sense as the right to demand obedience, but the prominent idea is to have power in exercise of control. Etymologically the word means superiority of the monarchs, because, sometimes it was considered as an exclusive preserve of the law church directly bestowed by God¹⁸.

In order to be consolidated in the law field, any state-legal phenomenon should be conceptualized, transferred into the category of legal structures. The sovereignty of the state is the legal construction that reveals the essence of the state authorities¹⁹. There is an intensive interaction between the sovereign's legal concept and its real implementation²⁰. Usually, Sovereignty is defined in one of two ways. The first definition applies to Supreme public power, which has right and in theory, the capacity to impose its authority in the holder of legitimate power, who is recognized to have authority²¹.

When national sovereignty is discussed, the first definition applies and it refers in particular to independence, understood as the freedom of a collective entity to act²². When popular sovereignty is discussed, the second definition applies, and sovereignty is associated with power and legitimacy²³. State sovereignty should not be overestimated; it is not absolute. Interstate communication leads to contacts and rapprochement of the position of the various states. This encourages interaction and interdependence, the

¹⁷ Garner A B, Black's Law Dictionary (9th Edition) p.1524.

¹⁸ George H.S, op cit note 16.

¹⁹ Yunk,B; et al; op cit note 15.

²⁰ Ibid page 579.

²¹ Alain D. B, *What is Sovereignty* p 99 accessed on the 16th April,2023:Also in Chayes, A.H; "*The New Sovereignty*"(Cambridge, Harvard University Press1995)

²²Alain, at page 99.

²³ Alain, at page 99.

searches for compromise and harmonization of national interests, which in some cases may involve certain concessions for the sake of peace and social progress²⁴.

It should be noted that only small but large countries have to adhere to the norms and the principles of international law, developed with their participation, as well as an intergovernmental agreement. As a result, the state in a certain extent constantly resorts to self-restraint on the issue of the implementation of its sovereign rights, which, however does not lead to the loss of sovereignty²⁵.

On the international level, sovereignty means independence, i.e., non-interference by external powers in the internal affairs of another state. International norms are based on the principle of the sovereign equality of independent state; International law excludes interference and establishes universally-accepted rules. Sovereignty depends not only on the autonomous will of its sovereign but on other sovereign states²⁶. From this perspective, one can say that sovereignty of any single state is the logical consequence of the existence of several foreign states.

2.1. ELEMENTS OF SOVEREIGNTY

The elements of sovereignty have been debatable by scholars as to what exactly it embodies. The reason was that all explanations were intended to justify either the hypothesis of the scholars or the political manipulation of the statement²⁷. Later on, rebellious secularism justifies it as a “supreme power over citizens and subjects unrestrained by law” it was later said to manifest itself in the general will of people and made wholly responsible for them.

Despite all these developments, sovereignty was limited by democrats, divided by pluralists and even discarded by anarchists; yet it maintained its basic tenets²⁸. The changes of the concept at international sphere met with challenge by other eminent concept like national self-determination whether state is actually a sovereign one or a certain political-territorial formation proclaims itself as a state that can be obtained only

²⁴Weiler J.H, op cit page 11.

²⁵ Ibid p 578.

²⁶ Op cit note 12 p 100.

²⁷ George H.S, Op cit note 15.

²⁸ Ibid, pg 1.

from the analyses of the practice of the implementation of sovereignty is concretized in sovereign rights²⁹.

It is generally known that sovereignty is concretized in sovereign but in legal science there is no correlation between the two, the state is characterized as sovereign but to find international legal instruments and national legislation linking it as such is rather difficult³⁰. More important for discussion of sovereign rights and its relationship with sovereignty is a constitutional legislation and international legal document regulating interstate relations in the political sphere³¹.

The principles of international law provide that state shall not be entitled to use or promote use of economic, political measures to subdue the other state in questioning the implementation of its sovereign right³². This is in line with the principle objectives of the WTO (Non-Discrimination and Most-Favored-Nation Principles) which emphasizes that members should be accorded equal treatment. This also refers to the principle of sovereign equality of states: all states are juridical equal; they have the same rights and responsibilities and are equal members of the international community, each state enjoys the right inherent in full sovereignty³³. Thus sovereign does not exclude the possibility of its implication by participating of the state in the activities of interstate unions³⁴.

The sovereignty of state cannot be identified with its powers and competence; it is a specific property of state power which cannot be measured in volume. It is possible to limit the government in the implementation of specific rights or competence, but it is impossible to limit the sovereignty³⁵. This revolution in international law has brought with it many new challenges. Perhaps the greatest is the increasingly salient tension between the ideal of state sovereignty and the notion of international order based on law. State sovereignty

²⁹ Op cit note 16.

³⁰ Ibid pg 579 (An exception from this rule was the constitutional law of the Soviet Union, which in constitution of 1936, and 1979 contained a statement that sovereign right of the union republics (Soviet Republics have been normally recognized as states) are protected by the USSR.

³¹ Ibid p 580.

³² Ibid p 580.

³³ Article 1 of the Final Act, on Security and Cooperation in Europe (1975) with amendments.

³⁴ Article 88 (2) of the constitution of French Republic which specifies that such participation is possible in compliance with the principle of Reciprocity. Culled from Goryunor.V (2007) "Sovereignty of the Russian Federation (the essence, content security) (PhD). Ural state law Academy accessed on the 1st July, 2023, at <https://.www.USLA.org.edu>.223.

³⁵ Pastukhov N, (2006) *State Sovereignty in the Era of Globalization. Magazine of the Russian Right*, 5 pg, 130-141.

requires that states have ultimate and independent authority to govern themselves and those within their territory. Yet states now routinely make legal promises that are perceived to lie in direct conflict with this conception of sovereignty, including delegating to international institutions authority that has traditionally been held exclusively by states. Much of the recent scholarly and public debate about international law has been motivated by these concerns. Beginning in the 1990s, a series of legal scholars criticized international law as posing a threat to state sovereignty³⁶.

Sometimes termed the "New Sovereignists,"³⁷ these scholars regard much of international law as a threat to both internal and external sovereignty. Though their precise objections to international law are many and varied, one central theme holds constant across these criticisms: Modern international law gives too much power to foreign states and international organizations, stripping authority from domestic lawmaking institutions³⁸. This is especially true of international agreements in which states grant authority to international bodies to make decisions or take actions in a process referred to as "international delegation."

There is a view that says state accession to the integration of associations leads to a limitation of state sovereignty. This conclusion is regarded as erroneous³⁹. There is a powerful tension between traditional core "sovereignty" and the international institution translated into the jurisprudence of the WTO dispute system⁴⁰. In the words of Kofi Annan: "our post-war institutions were built for inter-national world, but now we live in a global world" In a dangerous world marked by overwhelming inequalities of power and

³⁶ Some Of The Key Works In This Vein Include Jack L. Goldsmith & Eric A. Posner, *The Limits Of International Law* (2005); John C. Yoo, *The Powers Of War And Peace: The Constitution And Foreign Affairs After 9/11* (2005); Curtis A. Bradley, *A New American Foreign Affairs Law?*, 70 U. COLO. L. REV. 1089 (1999); Curtis A. Bradley & Jack L. Goldsmith, *Customary International Law as Federal Common Law: A Critique of the Modern Position*, 110 HARV. L. REV. 815 (1997).

³⁷ The term was coined by Peter Spiro in his excellent article, *The New Sovereignists: American Exceptionalism and Its False Prophets*, FOREIGN AFF., Nov.-Dec. 2000, at 9, available at <http://www.foreignaffairs.org/2000/6.html> (follow "The New Sovereignists" accessed April, 2023).

³⁸ For example, at a conference titled *Trends in Global Governance: Do They Threaten American Sovereignty?*, John Yoo, a professor at the University of California at Berkeley, cautioned that "[n]ovel forms of international cooperation increasingly call for the transfer of rulemaking authority to international organizations that lack American openness and accountability." *UN Wars, US War Powers*, 1 CHI. J. INT'L L. 355, 361(2000)

³⁹ *Ibid* p 135.

⁴⁰ *Op cit* note 3.

resources, sovereignty is for many states their best- and sometimes seemingly their only-life line defense⁴¹.

3.0. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The theory of sovereignty emerged as an attempt to identify and analyze the center of power in the society. Jaen Bodin was the first to develop the theory as “absolute and perpetual power within the state”⁴². According to him, power is without any restriction, unrestrained by law because sovereign is the law. The government is only strong when it is legitimate and its actions must be in accordance with certain norms determined by justice and that the capacity to make and break laws belongs only to the sovereign: the powers to legislate and rule are identical⁴³.

John Locke, attempted to democratize the word into ‘people’ general “well” purportedly place sovereignty into the hand of common man. The French Revolution in 1789 adopted these ideas which the state sovereign remain an arbitrary power resulting in poverty and superstition permitted⁴⁴.

Thomas Hobbes⁴⁵ reinforced the theory, he stated that since power is derived from rational will of all, the sovereign has the right to require total obedience from everyone since legitimacy stems from the fact that members of society have forfeited their sovereignty voluntarily which neither depends on person nor situations but stands on right and law. The people cannot oppose sovereign for possession of unlimited freedom of the state, the nature sovereignty is equal, indivisible and absolute⁴⁶.

Hegel (1770-1831)⁴⁷ also enunciated the theory of unlimited sovereignty in support of totalitarianism and expansionism. This theory became a threat to international legal order. The claim to unlimited external sovereignty would amount to the negation of international law and reduce it to a system of international morality⁴⁸.

⁴¹ Ibid at p.60.

⁴² George H S , op cit.

⁴³ Ibid at p378.

⁴⁴ Kenova E, *Early Recognition of the New State: Some Theoretical Aspects*. Journal of International Law and International Relationships. (2007). Vol.4 p 15-20.

⁴⁵Pastukhov N, op cit, p 104.

⁴⁶ Ibid page 105.

⁴⁷ George S, *Power Politics*; A study of World Society Stevens and Sons, London Press. (1964)

⁴⁸Ibid at p 92.

Global society which Althusius⁴⁹ calls the *integral symbolic community* is defined as an organization, ascending plurality of communities founded on prior association and multiple memberships, and disposing of overlapping powers. According to this view “what concerns all must be approved by all” *quod omnestangit, ab omnibus approbetur*. While sovereignty belongs to the people in perpetuity, it cannot be prescribed, however, it is not absolute on the contrary, and it can be distributed and shared. It only represents the level of power with the greatest capacity to decide and to execute a given task⁵⁰.

The sovereign cannot act willfully without being held accountable. This idea supports the notion where only the stakeholders are responsible to initiate anti-dumping actions where there is injury or threat to a product/good or established industry from exporting member state(s). These concepts as found in the theory of sovereignty can be placed effectively to suggest that a nation state participates actively in international agreements/treaties without losing either sovereign right to decide internal affairs nor be subject to external powers of multinational or supranational institutions like UN, WTO etc.

4.0. BASIC ELEMENTS OF SOVEREIGNTY IN RELATION TO WORLD TRADING SYSTEM

The doctrine of the state sovereignty has two essential characteristics, internal supremacy and external independence. In a classical perspective “sovereign state was one which exercised undivided authority over all persons and property within its borders and was independent of direct control of any other power, sovereignty implies independence all round, within and without the borders of the country⁵¹. Sovereignty is an essential feature of state power, it signifies “supremacy” of the state in its internal and independence in its external relations⁵².

Sovereignty is the supreme authority by any state governed. There was no power within the state which might compete with it. It possesses an exclusive competence and the relative independence of law making entities from outside intervention, how can these provisions relate with the criteria for the implementation of ADA? No subordination to a

⁴⁹Op cit note p 112.

⁵⁰ Ibid page 114.

⁵¹ Charles G F, *International Law*, New York Publication Series(1967) p 125.

⁵² Ibid ,DjuraNincil, *the Problem of sovereignty in the Charter and in practice of the United Nation* (Murtinus Nijhoff, The Hague, 1970) Accessed on 3rdApril, 2022. From < [www./https://UN/texts](https://www.un.org/https://UN/texts)> 126' p 201.

foreign authority in international sphere and in domestic affairs can assume predominance over any power vested in group or individuals within the state⁵³.

Sovereignty of the state appeared as a centralized power that exercised its lawmaking and law enforcing authority within a certain territory⁵⁴. This includes exclusiveness of the state powers within a certain territorial jurisdiction related to the power of legislation, adjudication and administration. The illimitability of sovereignty involved; the unlimited right to govern; the unlimited capacity to rule; the unlimited concentration of granted rights; unlimited authority within the domain of the state amongst others.

Another ingredient ensues which implied that Sovereignty has three main features: it is legal, absolute, and unitary condition. Invisibility constituted its main feature because the nature of its function could not afford the division. External independence was concomitant aspect of Sovereignty with its internal supremacy. The idea of Sovereignty was not final, absolute authority exists elsewhere; autonomy, independence, and equality were the three basic elements of Sovereignty as recognized by the norms of international relations⁵⁵. Non-intervention is another ingredient of Sovereignty as observed by the United Nation General Assembly in its resolution 1970⁵⁶.

“No state or group of states has the right to intervene, directly or indirectly, for any reason whatever, in the internal or external affairs of any other state. Consequently, armed intervention and all forms of interference ...are in violation of international law ...Every state has an inalienable right to choose its political, economic, social and cultural symbols, without interference in any form by another state...”

This principle signifies independence which must be observed for the states to survive in the international law sphere. It further brought equality among the nation states. All states

⁵³ Taylor P, “*Supranationalism the Point and Authority of International Institutions*; (1990) Frame work for International Cooperations, A.J.R Printer Publication London p 111.

⁵⁴ Ibid page 112.

⁵⁵ Ibid at p 114-40.

⁵⁶ Ibid at p 118-41.

enjoys Sovereign equally as members of the international community, notwithstanding differences of an economic, social, political or other nature⁵⁷.

5.0 EXCEPTIONS TO THE GENERAL RULE

Are there exceptions where sovereignty and international rights relinquished to justify commitment and respect for international norms without necessarily losing the said supremacy over internal and external affairs?

Although, all the concept ranging from exclusivity, supremacy, dominance, indivisibility, competence, etc. demand absolute compliance for states to be independent, there are situations where the general rule admits exceptions upon which the concepts may be relaxed. Other exception (modern theory) emerges to which submission does not divest state off their Sovereign powers. Both exceptions are discussed alongside each other. State sovereignty is best understood as a bundle of properties rather than as a single characteristic. Four of these properties stand out: (1) the authority to govern, (2) the supremacy of the governing authority, (3) the independence of the governing authority, and finally (4) the territoriality of the governing authority⁵⁸.

State Sovereignty confronted several challenges to its internal and external aspect of supremacy and independence from its inception. Even the founder of the theory, Bodin⁵⁹ conceded to this fact where he admitted that Sovereign is bound by the law of God and of nature. The exceptions are many but few would be considered in this research work. Rule of law, democratization and decentralization, pluralism, Rule of ideology, people's Sovereignty, federalism, self-determination are the general exceptions. There are special exceptions that directly shape the global trading system where states may be seen to be losing Sovereign rights but in practical sense they are not⁶⁰. The more popular exceptions are most upshots from consent and delegation of authority by member states;

⁵⁷ United Nations, Declaration on Principle of International Law Concerning Friendly Relations and Cooperation Among States in Accordance with Charter of the United Nations, Resolution 2625 (XXV), 24 October, 1970.

⁵⁸ Territoriality is a distinctive characteristic of modern *state* sovereignty. It means that each state is associated with a defined territorial space and each territorial space is associated with a particular governing state authority. Of course, the appropriate governing authority and precise territorial bounds may be contested. For example, both the states of India and Pakistan claim sovereignty over the territory of Kashmir. Indeed, the very fact that this is a significant source of conflict serves to illustrate how usual it is to have unsettled authority over any particular territorial space.

⁵⁹ Op cit note 39.

⁶⁰ Ibid 201.

5.1. CONSENT BY WHOM?

Under the principle of sovereign consent, a state can be required to follow the rules that an international agreement lays out only if it has voluntarily agreed to be bound⁶¹. This is an important fact for international delegation, because delegations are all made by international agreement. Thus the power to accept or reject an international agreement is the power to accept or reject a delegation of authority. Hence, this argument rests on an assumption that the body that is bound (the "state") is the same as that which consents. But this assumption is called into some question on closer inspection of *who* is consenting⁶².

5.2. TIME-INCONSISTENT PREFERENCES

There is a second and related difficulty with treating "state consent" to international delegation as the central answer is centered on how delegation might undermine domestic authority. States are not only made up of multiple actors who may have different preferences from one another. They are also made up of a shifting constellation of actors who may individually and collectively have different preferences across time⁶³.

5.3. UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES

When state grants authority to an international body to take action or make decisions that consent rests on a certain expectation of what the international body will do with the authority granted to it. But once the authority has been given away, states inevitably lose some control over the exercise of it. Hence, the authority states mean to delegate an international body which sometimes differ from the authority later exercised by that same international body. This might be called the problem of unintended consequences of delegation. The existence of such unintended consequences is perhaps the single most salient reason for the tension between international delegation and state sovereignty⁶⁴.

⁶¹ For more on the broader topic of the voluntary nature of treaties, see Oona A. Hathaway, *Between Power and Principle*, 72 U. CHI. L. REV. 469 (2005). See also Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties art. 34 ("A treaty does not create either obligations or rights for a third State without its consent."); RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF FOREIGN RELATIONS LAW OF THE UNITED STATES pt. I, introductory note, at 18 (1987) ("Modern international law is rooted in acceptance by states which constitute the system."); Louis HENKIN, INTERNATIONAL LAW: POLITICS AND VALUES 28 (1995) ("For treaties, consent is essential. No treaty, old or new, whatever its character or subject, is binding on a state unless it has consented to it.").

⁶² Ibid note 64.

⁶³ OONA, A; HATHAWAY, *International Delegation And State Sovereignty*. (2007) This article is also available at <http://law.duke.edu/journals/lcp>. accessed 15th april 2023* Associate Professor of Law, Yale Law School.

⁶⁴ This concept of unintended consequences is related to principal-agent slack, which has been extensively explored by political scientists and legal scholars in the areas of legislative and judicial decision making. See, e.g., Akhil Reed Amar,

5.4. ASYMMETRIC POWER;

The final point that complicates states' consent to international delegation concerns the context in which the consent is given. I have argued here that the voluntary character of most international delegations greatly reduces the risk of "sovereignty costs" arising from them. When there are significant asymmetries in power between the parties to an international delegation, the weaker party's consent may reflect the disproportionate influence of the stronger. The most familiar—and extreme instances of such asymmetric power are found when consent to a delegation is coerced. Less obvious, but more common today, are delegations generated when states with unequal power enter agreements that one or more of them simply cannot afford to refuse⁶⁵.

5.5. International Law;

International law comprises a system of institution and rules designed to govern international relations between Sovereign states. These rules impede the traditional expression of internal supremacy and absolute independence of Sovereign state. But to be Sovereign is not to be above the law⁶⁶; it's to be subject, from the moment of its foundation, to all the existing rules and obligations of international law⁶⁷.

Hence, external Sovereign does not mean 'supremacy' but equality of a Sovereign state to participate in the international system on a level of legal or formal equality with other members, this signifies independence in foreign policy within the framework of general international law ⁶⁸, and its bound by and to have an obligation under international law.

Conceptions which proclaim Sovereignty and international law as incompatible are scientifically invalid, irrespective of whether they proceeded from the position of absolute Sovereignty or negate it. International law regulates the conduct between members;

The Bill of Rights as a Constitution, 100 YALE L.J. 1131, 1206 (1990-1991); Akhil Reed Amar, *Of Sovereignty and Federalism*, 96 YALE L.J. 1425, 1432-37 (1986-1987); William R. Dougan & Michael C. Munger, *The Rationality of Ideology*, 32 J.L. & ECON. 119 (1989); Joseph P. Kalt & Mark A. Zupan, *The Apparent Ideological Behavior of Legislators: Testing for Principal-Agent Slack in Political Institutions*, 33 J.L. & ECON. 103 (1990); Joseph P. Kalt & Mark A. Zupan, *Capture and Ideology in the Economic Theory of Politics*, 74 AM. ECON. REV. 279 (1984); John McArthur & Stephen V. Marks, *Constituent Interest vs. Legislator Ideology: The Role of Political Opportunity Cost*, 26 ECON. INQUIRY 461 (1988)

⁶⁵Op cit note 66.

⁶⁶ Op cit note 40.

⁶⁷Ibid page 20.

⁶⁸ Ibid Page 20

hence there exist some norms which restrain certain powers in the interest of the community. State assumes corresponding obligations under international law.⁶⁹ International agreements and general obligations under international law do not normally constitute limitation on state Sovereignty. The idea that Sovereignty can neither be limited nor divided is contrary to modern developments in international society, yet cannot divest state from the absolute rights to control their economic, social and cultural norms internally and how they relate externally⁷⁰.

5.6. International Organizations;

The institutional aspects of organizations of states pose serious challenge to the principle of Sovereign equality of member states. Various organs of the organizations may be permitted to take decisions, or even make binding rules, with or without express consent of all or any of the member states. However, this organization is an association of states established on the basis of a treaty and in accordance with international law in order to achieve specific objectives possessing a system of organs and right and duties that are distinct from those of member states⁷¹.

5.7. Complex World Economy;

Complex world economy has begun to cast serious doubts on claims of state Sovereignty. International trade, credit and financial relations, transportation and industrial co-operation among nations have risen to immense proportions. The system of international trade produces a specialized economic pattern which seems largely unaffected by administrative decisions and actions at the level of government. In the interest of international economic security, the emphasis is always on, "how promptly and effectively individual countries agree to subordinate their national Sovereignty and independence to the interests of international monopoly capital"⁷².

These concepts proved the independence of member-states to regulate internal policies, socially, economically and culturally. Anti-Dumping Agreement falls within this sphere under the WTO Agreement. States needs to exercise a policy that would be more

⁶⁹ Ibid Page 30.

⁷⁰ Op cit note 47.

⁷¹ Op cit note 38 Page 126.

⁷² Valentine. S; *Transnational Corporations and Doctrine of Neoglobalism*; Allied Publishers, New Delhi, (1987) p125.

responsive to promote development of a new form of Sovereignty. This focuses on those aspect as to content which would allow state actively develop international communication without compromising its foundation⁷³.

Under the influence of globalization, states increasingly agree to transfer their own certain Sovereign right to supranational jurisdictions and associations including international organizations: United Nations, Council of Europe, CSCE, NATO, and WTO. This gives rise to a qualitative implementation of Sovereign rights. Constitution of a number of states also contains provisions relating to the implementation of Sovereign right of membership in the intergovernmental associations⁷⁴, the transfers by the state of certain Sovereign rights does not mean the restriction of Sovereign rights. States under WTO possess the right to make decision, modify constitution, legislate on certain government authorities, citizenship, currency, collection of taxes and fees, establishment of territorial division, regulate natural resources, law enforcement etc. these constitutes the basis of Sovereign state internally⁷⁵. External Sovereignty on the other hand, disclose the right to conclude international treaties and agreements, establishment of diplomatic relations, participation in international organization like WTO, declaration of war and conclusion of peace, right to neutrality etc. These attributes still exist and WTO member states have control over them⁷⁶.

States independently develop and enter into contracts, signing and transfer certain Sovereign rights. Such transfer only signifies right to form voluntary self-limitation of its own jurisdiction⁷⁷. Sovereignty may not do justice to the contemporary status of global market integration because there are plausible risks that protectionists may seek refuge in an overarching claim of sovereignty⁷⁸. At times powerful countries tend to summon the

⁷³ Op cit note 16.

⁷⁴ Ibid ;and Sections 15,16,17 and 19 of Nigeria's Constitution 1999(as amended)

⁷⁵ Ibid, well covered under Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy of Nigeria's Constitution,1999(as amended)

⁷⁶ Ibid p 583.

⁷⁷ Ibid p 587.

⁷⁸ Ibid at p 668.

ill-defined concept of veto to do away with compliance or cooperation within an international organization⁷⁹.

It is imperative that in this highly interdependent international environment, trading nations, even the most powerful ones, to involve a degree of intrusiveness into domestic governance which also necessitates cooperative mechanisms, appropriate allocation of power between international institutions and diverse national legal system⁸⁰. Making ADA to be domesticated but consistent with the main text of WTO further confirms this argument.

6.0. FINDINGS

The WTO is overextended and in danger of losing authority and legitimacy as the arbiter of trade dispute among the world's major trading nations⁸¹. The WTO had shifted from GATT model of negative regulation—what governments must not do—to positive regulations, or what government must do⁸².

This is not to suggest that the *Asbestos* controversy stands for the rejection of private party participation in the international legal order—far from it. Rather, it stands for the principle that states will continue to determine who may participate in that order. In some cases, states have delegated that determination to international organizations, either tacitly or explicitly, and the amicus practice of many international tribunals reflects part of the outcome of that delegation. At the same time, the *Asbestos* controversy demonstrates that there will be other situations where states (and other entities possessing international sovereignty) reserve the right to make that determination on their own⁸³.

This body of international jurisprudence sometimes conflicts with the actions of U.S. administrative agencies responsible for the regulation of international trade. U.S. courts

⁷⁹ Ibid at p 669.

⁸⁰ John H J, *International Economic Law in Times That are Interesting*, 3 Journal of International Economic Law (2000) p 6.

⁸¹ Barfield E Claude, op cit.

⁸² Sylvia Ostry, WTO: *Institutional Design for Better Governance*, available online at <<http://www.ksg.harvard.edu/cbg/trade/ostry.html>> (visited April 17, 2023)

⁸³ WTO membership, for example, is not limited to states. A number of non-state actors are WTO members, e.g., Hong Kong and the European Communities, having the same rights and duties under the WTO Agreement as states, although the EC does not have a vote separate from and in addition to its Member states. See WTO Agreement, arts. IX, XII, XIV.

confronted this conflict between WTO panel decisions and U.S. administrative agency actions with two competing doctrines:

(1) the Chevron doctrine,⁸⁴ which dictates that a court will give great deference to an administrative agency's interpretation of ambiguous congressional legislation, complemented by a general judicial deference to executive actions in foreign affairs, and (2) the *Charming Betsy* doctrine,⁸⁵ which encourages courts to interpret legislation, including treaties, so as not to violate international law. In the context of this comment, both of these doctrines are seen as interpretive canons.

Interpretive canons are tools that courts use to decide between different possible interpretations of an ambiguous statute or treaty. Courts apply the law, and sometimes Congress leaves a statute open to various possible interpretations. Congress may do so either because it wishes to avoid the political costs of clearly speaking on an issue or because the subject matter of the legislation is extremely complex and the executive branch⁸⁶ has a unique institutional competence in a particular area.

Under international trade law, congressional action (in the form of treaties and statutes) is often lacking in detail regarding the implementation of U.S. trade policies. This can lead to a conflict between a WTO panel decision about obligations under an international agreement and a U.S. administrative agency's assessment of those same obligations.

This commitment will:

- (1) explain the leading U.S. federal court precedent in addressing the conflict between WTO panel decisions and executive action in antidumping regulation;
- (2) Briefly summarize the reasoning behind the precedent and the counter arguments to that reasoning; and
- (3) Propose a consistent approach to the application of WTO panel decisions in litigation involving interpretation of the Anti-Dumping Agreement and its implementing legislation.

⁸⁴ *Chevron U.S.A., Inc. v. Natural Resources Dcr Council. Inc.*, 4(,7 U.S. X37, X42 X43 (19~4). See Discussion, Part IV.B.1.

⁸⁵ *Murray v. Schooner Charming Betsy*, (, U.S. 64, 11 K (1 K(4). See discussion *op cit* Part IV.B.2.

⁸⁶ For the purposes of this comment, the executive branch of the U.S. government includes all of the administrative agencies responsible for the enforcement and implementation of congressional legislation. Thus, the terms "executive," the "Commerce Department" (or simply "Commerce"), and the "International Trade Administration" ("Trade Administration") all possess essentially the same relationship to the judiciary and Congress.

It is argued that WTO panel decisions should be given more weight than they are now; panel decisions should set up a presumption of the reasonableness or unreasonableness of executive interpretation of Congressional legislation. This presumption could be rebutted by evidence of a pressing need for a court to defer to the executive under traditional political deference doctrines. The transfer of the state of certain sovereign rights and authorities to supranational structures does not mean the restriction of sovereign rights. The transferred right compensated by the acquisition of the so called system-wide authority. As a result, the limit of the overall activity of the states is expanding significantly.

7.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Altering international context requires a more flexible concept of sovereignty which departs from the old passion. Nations should adopt the “new sovereignty” which is more mature, constructive, and participatory so that trade norms should be “disaggregated” to make possible to assess the relative advantages and disadvantages of reinforcing particular norms⁸⁷. This approach will enable government to identify and focus on important “policy” issues that confront the entire international community and also help government achieve its objective in international obligations⁸⁸law making within the domestic appears of any WTO member is akin to its sovereign power but can be sub-delegated for international cohesion and economic prosperity.

It is recommended that any participation in Multi-Lateral Agreements like ADA being a trade relief should be based on individual’s membership peculiarity to ease preposition that members are losing sovereign rights to international organizations and multi-corporations. The paper also recommends the abolition of *Amicus Curie* at Dispute Settlement cases and allow for full participation of member state’s actors before final determination at panel and appellate bodies of the WTO. Further, member states should adopt U.S. approach in resolving conflicting issues within its jurisdiction by applying the competing two doctrines- the *Chevron and Charming Betsy*. This approach gives the

⁸⁷ H.J. *The Great 1994 Sovereignty Debate: The United States Acceptance and Implementation of the Uruguay Round Results*, 36 (1994). P 157 and 187-188.

⁸⁸Op cit note 62 at p 670.

concept of “new sovereignty” a wider acceptability through courts system of interpreting international agreements.